

Mini Research Proposal and Mini Research Report

Format of Mini Research Proposal

Preliminary Part

Cover page [title, details of the researcher (name, email, designation, affiliation), and date/year]

Table of Contents

Acronyms/Abbreviations

List of Tables (If necessary)

List of Figures (If necessary)

CHAPTER I: Introduction (परिचय)

Background of the Study (अध्ययनको भूमिका)

Statement of the Problem (समस्या कथन)

Objectives of the Study (अध्ययनको उद्देश्य)

Research Question/s (if necessary) (अनुसन्धान प्रश्न)

Significance of the Study (अध्ययनको महत्व)

Delimitations of the Study (अध्ययनको परिसिमा)

Definition of the Key Terms (मुख्य शब्दावलीहरूको परिभाषा)

CHAPTER II: Review of Related Literature and Theoretical Framework

Review of Related Literature (सम्बन्धित पूर्व साहित्यको समिक्षा)

Conceptual/Theoretical (धारणात्मक/सैद्धान्तिक)

Empirical (अनुभवजन्य)

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework (सैद्धान्तिक/धारणात्मक रूपरेखा)

Implications of the Review for the literature (सम्बन्धित पूर्व साहित्यको समिक्षाको उपयोग)

CHAPTER III: Methods and Procedures (विधि र प्रक्रिया)

Research Design (Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Design) (अध्ययनको ढाँचा)

Population and Sample (जनसंख्या र नमूना)

Research Tools (अनुसन्धानका साधन)

Sources of Data (तथ्यको श्रोत)

Data Collection Procedures (तथ्य संकलनको प्रक्रिया)

Data Analysis Procedures (तथ्य विश्लेषणको प्रक्रिया)

Manpower planning (जनशक्ति योजना)

Scheduling of time (समय तालिका)

Budgeting/Estimated expenses (बजेट/अनुमानित खर्च)

Chapter plan/Organization of the Report (अध्याय योजना)

Ethical Considerations (नैतिकता सम्बन्धी विचार)

References (APA 7th format) (सन्दर्भसूची)

Appendices (List of respondents, tools, letter of consent etc.) (परिशिष्ट)

[Body of the text: Font-Times New Roman 12 (Preeti 14); Line spacing-1.5; APA 7th format in Paragraphing, Spacing, Citation, Tables, Figures, and Heading levels]

Format of Mini Research Report

Preliminary Part

Cover page [title, details of the researcher (name, email, phone no, designation, affiliation)].

Declaration

Evaluation and Approval

Acknowledgements

Abstract (topic, major objectives, method and procedure, main findings and key recommendations of the study within 350 word-limit).

Table of Contents

Acronyms/Abbreviations

List of Tables (If necessary)

List of Figures (If necessary)

List of Charts and Graphs (If necessary)

CHAPTER I: Introduction

Background of the study

Statement of the problem

Objectives of the study

Research question/s (if necessary)

Significance of the Study

Delimitations of the study

Definition of the key terms

CHAPTER II: Review of Related Literature and Theoretical Framework

Review of Related Literature

 Conceptual/Theoretical

 Empirical

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

Implications of the Review for the Research

CHAPTER III: Methods and Procedures

Research Design

Population and Sample

Research Tools

Sources of Data

Data Collection Procedures

Data Analysis Procedures

Ethical Considerations

CHAPTER IV: Results and Discussion

(Presentation and discussion of results should be based on the research questions or on the themes derived from the analytical framework.)

CHAPTER V: Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

Summary of findings

Conclusions

Recommendations

References (APA 7th format)

Appendices (List of respondents, tools, letter of consent etc.)

